

The Study of Mool Mantra Chanting of Guru Nanak Dev Ji on Adolescence Mental Health – An Experimental study

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Abstract:

This study aimed to examine the effect of Mool Mantra chanting on the mental health of adolescents aged 16–19. Rooted in the teachings of Guru Nanak Dev Ji, the Mool Mantra is considered a powerful spiritual invocation. A total of 50 students from Akal College of Physical Education, Sangrur, Punjab, were randomly selected and divided into experimental ($n = 25$) and control ($n = 25$) groups. The experimental group practiced chanting the Mool Mantra with Its Meaning daily for 15 minutes over a two-month period, while the control group maintained their routine lifestyle. Mental health was measured using the Mental Health Continuum–Short Form Scale (MHC-SF), which assesses emotional, psychological, and social well-being. Results showed a statistically significant improvement in the experimental group's post-test scores ($M = 51.92$) compared to pre-test ($M = 42.92$), $t(24) = -4.42$, $p = 0.00018$, with a large effect size ($\eta^2 = 0.44$). The control group showed no significant change ($p = 0.766$). These findings suggest that regular chanting of the Mool Mantra can significantly enhance mental health in adolescents. The study highlights the potential of spiritual practices as complementary tools for promoting psychological well-being among youth.

Keywords: Mantra Chanting, Mental Health, Adolescence, Guru Nanak Dev ji.

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1. Introduction-

Guru Nanak Dev Ji has been accepted by the scriptures and scholars as the author of the Mool Mantra. The Mool Mantra is located first in the beginning of Sri Guru Granth Sahib. The specialties of the Lord have been mentioned in this basic mantra, this is also a kind of invocation. Since ancient times, while starting any composition, writers used to offer invocation to their favorite gods and goddesses. That is why many such scriptures exist in India in the form of invocation of mantras, such as Ganesh Mantra and Gayatri Mantra, which are chanted with full devotion. The Mool Mantra of Guru Nanak Dev ji has such power that it is capable of removing all the troubles of life. This Mool Mantra is such that it is capable of removing the sins of many births. By chanting the Mool Mantra, any being can reach the state of bliss. When the veil between the soul and God is removed, only a visible form remains in front. The duality goes away. Above the three Gunas (Satva, Raj, Tamas), the Sahaj state of the fourth can be easily reached by the practice of chanting the mantra. Guru Nanak Dev ji teachings begin with this Mool Mantra. In other words, this mantra is the core of the teachings of Sri Guru Granth Sahib.¹ The eternal characteristics described in this mantra belong only to the one and only Almighty God. The whole world has arisen from that one. It is from these special qualities of God that humans have originated.

Literature Review

The word 'Japu' present in the Starting of this Mool Mantra is an order to chant and remember the name of God. In which it is Mentioned that by remembering the name or chanting the name in this world, one gets happiness not only here but also in the next world.² Simran is such a lamp, by doing which the flame of soul can merge into the flame of God. This is the real worship, by chanting even ego goes away. While discussing knowledge with Siddha Yogis, Guru Nanak Dev Ji has called the word Guru as the best in all the four eras.³ By practicing which even worldly vices cannot have any effect on the devotees. Generally, human mind is entangled in illusion. But by changing the name, man gets liberated from these vices. I found no Any Practical study has been conducted concern with my topic before this research only theoretical explanations available in some sacred books Sri Granth Sahib ji, Mool Mantra Vichar, and an article written by Dev Swroop Kour Khalsa.⁴

Aims and Objective-

Aim – Examine the effect of Mool Mantra chanting on Adolescence Mental Health.

Objectives -

- Evaluate the effect of Mool Mantra chanting on Adolescence Psychological Well-Being.
- Evaluate the effect of Mool Mantra chanting on Adolescence Social Well-Being.
- Evaluate the effect of Mool Mantra chanting on Adolescence Emotional Well-Being.

Hypothesis-

Null Hypothesis-

There is No any Effect of Mool Mantra chanting on Adolescence Mental Health.

Alternate Hypothesis -

The Mool Mantra chanting Effect on Adolescence Mental health.

2. Material and Methods -

Firstly The Adolescence students (16- 19 years) were selected for the Target population, then the sample selection was done through G Power Software, to get 0.5 percent efficacy of Paired t-Test and Mental Health Continuum Scale for measurement of Mental health of Adolescence. For this, the Ideal number of students for the sample was obtained through G Power Software.

The 50 Students were selected by simple randomization method and divided into two groups of 25 in each One out of 200 (B.P.E.S. - 1st& 2Nd Year) Students Akal College of Physical Education, Sangrur

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Punjab. In which one was identified as control group and the other as experimental group for two months from 01/10/2022 to until 30/11/2022. Researcher himself practiced the experimental group to chanting the Mool Mantra 21 times with its meaning for 15 Minutes at 7:00 am in Class Room. Consent was taken from Participants before Starting the Research. Whereas the control group was recommended to adopt the same lifestyle. As an external variable, the control group was prohibited from undertaking any new spiritual activities specially related to chanting, and the results of the research were obtained by analyzing the data collected before and after two months.

Inclusion Criteria - Only those students were selected who were not practicing any spiritual practice.

Exclusions Criteria - The research did not include students who were practicing any other form of spirituality Practice.

Variables and Measurement - The chanting of the Mool Mantra has been taken as an independent variable along with its meaning that is described in Sri Guru Granth Sahib Darpan written by Professor Sahib Singh (Translator Bhupendra Singh Bhaikhel)

Ikk Omkar Satnam Karta Purakh Nirbhau Nirbair Akal Murt Ajooni Saibham Gur Prasad.⁵ (Mool Mantra)

Meaning - There is one God, who is the complete truth. He who is the creator of the entire universe is omnipresent. He is free from fear and malice. His form is beyond the bondage of birth and death. He does belong to any Origination Point. It is self-illuminated, and can be attained only by the grace of the Guru.

(MHC-SF Scale): The Mental Health Continuum Short Form Scale

Mental Health has been taken as the dependent variable. Mental health has been assessed on the basis of three important dimensions of (Social, Emotional & Psychological Well Being).The Mental Health Continuum Scale (MHC) used for the measurement of Mental Health. The Cronbach's Alpha Value of this Scale is .91 & it is an authentic scale – (MHC-SF Scale Developed by Corey L. Keyes)⁶

पिछले महीने के दौरान आपको कितनी बार महसूस हुआ -	कभी नहीं	एक या दो बार	सप्ताह में एक बार	सप्ताह में दो या तीन बार	लगभग प्रत्येक दिन	प्रतिदिन
1.आनंद						
2.जीवन में रुचि रखते हैं						
3.जीवन से संतुष्ट						
4.कि आप के पास समाज में योगदान करने के लिए कुछ महत्वपूर्ण था						
5.कि आप एक समुदाय से संबंधित थे (जैसे कि एक सामाजिक समूह, या आपके पड़ोस)						
6. कि हमारा समाज एक अच्छी जगह है, या सभी लोगों के लिए बेहतर जगह बन रहा है						
7.कि लोग मूल रूप से अच्छे हैं						
8.कि जिस तरह से हमारा समाज काम करता है आपको समझ में आता है						
9.कि आप अपने व्यक्तित्व के अधिकांश विशेषताओं को पसंद करते हैं						
10.अपने दैनिक जीवन की जिम्मेदारियों को अच्छे से प्रबंधित कर रहे हैं						
11.कि आपके दूसरों के साथ स्नेहपूर्ण और विश्वसनीय रिश्ते थे						
12.कि आपके अनुभवों ने आपको विकसित और एक अच्छा व्यक्ति बनने की चुनौती दी थी □						

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13.आप अपने विचारों और मर्तों को अभिव्यक्त करने एवं सोचने में आशुस्त हैं						
14.कि आपके जीवन में दिशा या अर्थ की समझ है						

The Above Shown questionnaire have 14 questions in Mental Health Continuum Scale, in which there are 6 responses in the form of answer for each question, out of all these responses, the respondent has to mark one response, and thus The score of Mental Health of the provider is determined by adding the responses received on all the questions. The minimum score of Mental Health Continuum Scale is -0 and the maximum score is -70, the selection and measurement of answers to the questions is as follows - (Never - 0, Once or twice - 1, Once a week - 2, Two or three times a week - 3, Almost every day - 4, Everyday - 5) (Likart Scale).

Collection and Presentation of data -The Data collection was done through a questionnaire of 14 questions provided in the Mental Health Continuum Scale For obtain the Mental Health Score. The response received on each question from each participant was marked on the basis of a marking system of 0-5, after that by adding the responses received on all the questions. The level of mental health of the participant was assessed, and finally the data was obtained by calculating the Mental Health Score of the participants in pre-test and post-test sequence. The participants of experimental group and control group belong to the same population and Shapiro-Wilk test Shows P Value larger than 0.05. Therefore, paired t-test through SPSS & Cohen's 1988 Effect Size Test was used to analyze the data.

Paired Samples Statistics					
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Experimental Pre-Data	42.92	25	9.937	1.987
	Experimental Post Data	51.92	25	4.932	0.986
Pair 2	Control Pre-Data	42.40	25	7.969	1.594
	Control Post Data	41.84	25	7.603	1.521

Table - 1

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Experimental Pre Data - Experimental Post Data	-9	10.2	2.04	-13.199	-4.8	-4.42	24	0.00018
Pair 2	Control Pre Data - Control Post Data	0.56	9.32	1.86	-3.287	4.41	0.3	24	0.766

Table-2

P Value < 0.05, Hence Null Hypothesis is Rejected.

Value of t (0.05) at 24(df) = 2.0849 (Tabulated), the obtained t Value of the Experimental Group is larger than that. Therefore, the difference is significant between the Experimental group and the control group.

Graph 01

Graph 02

Graph 03

3. Result –

A paired samples t-test was conducted to examine the effect of the intervention on participants' performance in the experimental group compared to the control group.

Experimental Group:

Participants in the experimental group (N = 25) had a mean pre-test score of 42.92 (SD = 9.94) and a mean post-test score of 51.92 (SD = 4.93). The mean increase of 9.00 points was found to be statistically significant, $t(24) = -4.42$, $p = 0.00018$, with a 95% confidence interval of the difference ranging from -13.20 to -4.80. This indicates a substantial improvement following the intervention.

Control Group:

In contrast, the control group (N = 25) had a mean pre-test score of 42.40 (SD = 7.97) and a mean post-test score of 41.84 (SD = 7.60). The slight decrease of 0.56 points was not statistically significant, $t(24) = 0.30$, $p = 0.766$, with a 95% confidence interval from -3.29 to 4.41.

4. Discussion-

The results suggest that the intervention administered to the experimental group had a significant positive effect on participant performance. The significant increase in post-test scores, coupled with the low standard deviation, indicates not only improvement but also reduced variability in outcomes after the intervention. In contrast, the control group showed no significant change in scores, suggesting that the observed improvement in the experimental group was likely due to the intervention itself rather than external factors or chance. These findings support the efficacy of the implemented intervention and its potential to enhance performance in similar settings. The lack of improvement in the control group reinforces the conclusion that the observed gains in the experimental group were not due to natural progression or test-retest effects.

The Effect Size Calculation of Obtain Data- The results obtained from the paired t-test can easily conclude whether the interventions affected the Mental Health of the students or not, but these results do not Shows Effect regarding the intensity Area of Intervention. The Effect Size Formula developed by Cohen in 1988 is used here for get More Accurate Results.

Formula: $= t^2 / t^2 + (N-1)$,

t = Obtain t Value, N= Number of Participants

t= -4.423, N= 25

Eta Squared $= (-4.423)^2 / (-4.423)^2 + (25-1)$,

$= 19.56 / 19.56 + (24)$,

$= 19.56 / 43.56$,

Eta Squared = 0.44 (Experimental Group)

Calculating Effect Size of Control Group (Eta Squared) = 0.003

The guidelines (proposed by Cohen 1988) for interpreting this value are.

.01-small effect, .06-moderate effect, 0.14-large effect.

5. Conclusion –

The results of the paired samples analysis indicate that the intervention had a significant positive impact on the performance of the experimental group. Participants in this group showed a statistically significant improvement from pre-test to post-test ($p = 0.00018$), with an average increase of 9 points. In contrast, the control group exhibited no significant change in performance ($p = 0.766$), suggesting that natural variation or repeated testing did not account for the gains seen in the experimental group. The t-value obtained using paired t-test was more than the table t-value, the value of p was less than 0.05, and this shows the significance of chanting the Mool Mantra on the experimental group. The Results of Effect Size Formula developed by Cohen 1988 was also positive. Our null hypothesis has been rejected; hence, we can say that chanting the Mool Mantra Chanting has a positive effect on Mental Health.

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